

TO STUDY THE CLINICAL EFFICACY OF PATHOGENETIC THERAPY IN WOMEN WITH GENITAL ENDOMETRIOSIS.

Mukhammadjonova M.M.

Gafurova F.A.

Center for the Development of Professional Qualifications of Medical Workers,
Department of Obstetrics, Gynecology and Perinatal Medicine, Tashkent
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Introduction.

Endometriosis is a chronic hormone—dependent disease characterized by an inflammatory reaction [1,2]. The chronic, progressive, and recurrent nature of endometriosis makes it extremely urgent to search for new areas of targeted therapy for genital endometriosis that have high therapeutic efficacy and minimal side effects. Currently, the standard for specific therapy of endometriosis is the use of dienogest 2 mg, which is a hybrid progestogen that combines the best properties of the norsteroid and progesterone groups [5,7]. Currently, the main goal of modern therapy for genital endometriosis is not only the suppression of the level of estrogens synthesized by the ovaries, but also the pathogenetic effect on the site of endometriosis itself (suppression of local estrogen production, overcoming progesterone resistance, antiproliferative and antiangiogenic effects, increased apoptosis).

The purpose of the study – to conduct a comparative assessment of the effectiveness of alternative pathogenetic therapy for endometriosis.

Materials and methods.

A study was conducted on 40 women by forming two comparison groups. In the group of women receiving dienogest and letrozole, dynamic control of the regression of endometriosis foci was performed. All drugs were administered orally daily for 24 weeks, after which a re-evaluation of the size of the endometrioid implants was performed.

Results and Discussion.

At the randomization stage, the average diameters of endometrioid implants were comparable in all groups. A comparative assessment of the effectiveness of the drugs with the control group and a comparison between the groups were carried out. The average area of endometrioid implants was significantly lower in all treated groups compared with the control group ($p < 0.05$, Fischer's criterion).

The most pronounced reduction in the size of endometrioid implants was observed in the group of women receiving dienogest. Dynamic monitoring revealed a decrease in the size of foci in more than half of the examined – 54%, no regression of foci was noted in 8% of patients. In the group of women who were prescribed letrozole, regression of foci in terms of diameter reduction parameters was observed in 48%. There was a significant reduction in the size of endometrioid implants compared to the control group, with no statistically significant difference between the groups.

Conclusion.

The study confirms the current lack of oral medications for the treatment of endometriosis that are comparable in efficacy and safety to dienogest. It is necessary to further study the various schemes for the use of non-hormonal drugs as an adjunct to classical hormone-modulating therapy for endometriosis or as monotherapy in patients with contraindications to standard hormonal therapy.

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